

Birds of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment, an opportunity for birders

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Keywords

Ad hoc observations, Birding hotspot, BirdLife South Africa, Citizen science, Conservation concern, Full protocol cards, Habitat diversity (including kloof forest, grasslands, and riverine habitats), KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE), Lüneburg, Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Authority (MTPA), Paardeplaas Nature Reserve, 2nd South African Bird Atlas Project (SABAP2), Wakkerstroom

Executive Summary: Birds of the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment

The KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE), a 30,000ha area in Mpumalanga near Lüneburg, represents a significant but under-surveyed opportunity for South African birding. While situated only 50km from the famous Wakkerstroom hotspot, the KPE offers a distinct and more diverse range of habitats, including kloof forest patches, pristine grasslands, and riverine environments.

Key Findings

Biodiversity: The KPE supports 17 bird species of conservation concern.

Unique Species: Data analysis reveals 30 species present in the KPE that are not found in Wakkerstroom, likely due to the KPE's greater habitat variety.

Survey Gaps: The area is currently under-recorded compared to its neighbour; while Wakkerstroom has 1,384 Full Protocol (Fp) cards and 322 species, the KPE has only 229 Fp cards and 236 species.

Rare Sightings: 56 species have been recorded only once or twice, including "specials" such as Botha's Lark, African Spoonbill, and Jacobin's Cuckoo.

Current Status and Challenges

The KPE is primarily comprised of privately owned land dedicated to livestock farming, commercial forestry, and crop cultivation, with the exception of the state-owned Paardeplaas Nature Reserve. The current management plan (2025–2030) guides conservation efforts.

A critical concern highlighted is the funding risk facing the SABAP2 database, which is the primary source for this birding data and a cornerstone of collaborative conservation in Africa.

Conclusion

The report concludes that the KPE is a "poorly surveyed" region with high potential for new observations. Birders are encouraged to visit and contribute to the SABAP2 database to help document this rugged and ecologically rich terrain.

Introduction

The KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE) is situated in Mpumalanga, about 50km from the well-known Wakkerstroom birding hotspot. The KPE covers approximately 30,000ha near Lüneburg. The first phase of the protected environment declaration was gazetted in 2010. The land is privately owned, except for the Paardeplaas Nature Reserve, which is owned by the Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Authority (MTPA). Details are available in the current Management Plan (MTPA 2025). The plan lists 17 bird species of conservation concern occurring in the area. Commercial farming activities are the order of the day with free-range livestock (cattle and sheep), some commercial forestry, and cash-crop cultivation.

For the purpose of this report, four pentads in the SABAP2 database were identified to represent, as closely as possible, the KPE. These are 2710_3025, 2710_3030, 2715_3025 and 2715_3030. Figure 1 shows their relationship with the towns of Wakkerstroom, Lüneburg, and Dirkiesdorp.

Figure 1. Location of the pentads relative to Wakkerstroom. From https://sabap2.birdmap.africa/coverage/group/459_KwmndIngmps.

While new records are being submitted continuously, statistics were extracted from the SABAP2 database on 2026-01-17 and are summarised in Table 1. Compared with Wakkerstroom, this area is very poorly surveyed, with only 229 Fps. Many new observations need to be recorded. The same can be said for the number of species, with a difference of almost 100.

Pentads 2710_3025 and 3715_3030 are particularly poorly represented, probably because of the difficulty of getting to sites in this rugged terrain.

Table 2 is a checklist of Fp and Ad records, listed alphabetically by common name. The list includes 17 bird species of conservation concern.

Table 3 lists the 56 birds that have been recorded only once or twice on Fp or Ad cards. Included here are specials like Botha's lark, African spoonbill and Jacobin's Cuckoo.

The most interesting finding from this analysis is in Table 4. There are 30 species that occur in the KPE but not at Wakkerstroom. Although interesting, this is unsurprising given the far greater diversity of habitats within the protected environment. Although Wakkerstroom boasts a large wetland, it lacks kloof forest patches, extensive pristine grasslands, and riverine habitats. Is there a better reason for visiting this area?

Acknowledgements

This report, and many like it, could not have been produced without the SABAP2 database. Unfortunately, the future of this invaluable source is at risk as funding sources dry up. SABAP2 is among the most successful collaborative conservation efforts in Africa, and its loss would entail not only the infrastructure but also the momentum and community that took nearly two decades to build. If you can help, contact sabap2@birdlife.org.za.

Lettie Morris has been visiting the area since she was five. She is an enthusiastic citizen scientist with interests in botany and birdlife, and is a champion of invader eradication on and around the farm she visits. She has submitted 58 SABAP2 lists, included in this report, since 2011.

Thanks to Duncan McKenzie and Roy Robertson for help with this report. The photographs are from warwicktarboton.co.za, with permission.

Reference

MTPA (2025) KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment Five-Year Management Plan:2025 – 2030. Unpublished report, Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency, Nelspruit, South Africa.

Some of the special birds of the KPE. Photographs ©Warwick Tarboton

Kingfisher, Half-collared

Chat, Buff-streaked

Cisticola, Pale-crowned

Blue Crane

Crane, Wattled

Blackcap, Bush

Ibis, Southern Bald

Francolin, Red-winged

Abbreviations used here.

Ad	Ad hoc observation
Adn	Number of Ad's
Fp	Full protocol card
Fpn	Number of Fp's
KPE	KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment
MTPA	Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Agency
Pentad	A 5-minute x 5-minute coordinate grid superimposed over the continent for spatial reference
Ref	Roberts' bird number
SABAP2	2nd South African Bird Atlas Project

Table 1. Summary statistics for the four pentads with the Wakkerstroom pentad for comparison.

Pentad	FP	Number of species
2710-3025 KPE	3	89
2710_3030 KPE	40	191
2715_3025 KPE	18	170
2715_3030 KPE	12	188
Combined pentads	229	236
2720_3005 Wakkerstroom	1384	322

Table 2. Checklist of the birds of the KPE as of January 2026 from SABAP2.

Ref	Common name	Scientific name	Fp	Fpn	Ad	Adn
622	Apalis, Bar-throated	<i>Apalis thoracica</i>	50.7	37	4.7	5
431	Barbet, Black-collared	<i>Lybius torquatus</i>	63.0	46	22.4	24
439	Barbet, Crested	<i>Trachyphonus vaillantii</i>	37.0	27	15.0	16
672	Batis, Cape	<i>Batis capensis</i>	39.7	29	6.5	7
673	Batis, Chinspot	<i>Batis molitor</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
410	Bee-eater, Little	<i>Merops pusillus</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
810	Bishop, Yellow	<i>Euplectes capensis</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
812	Bishop, Yellow-crowned	<i>Euplectes afer</i>	5.5	4	0.9	1
542	Blackcap, Bush	<i>Lioptilus nigricapillus</i>	9.6	7	0.0	0
722	Bokmakierie	<i>Telophorus zeylonus</i>	60.3	44	24.3	26
709	Boubou, Southern	<i>Laniarius ferrugineus</i>	38.4	28	4.7	5
546	Brownbul, Terrestrial	<i>Phyllastrephus terrestris</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
11491	Bulbul, Common	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	2.7	2	1.9	2
545	Bulbul, Dark-capped [x]	<i>Pycnonotus tricolor</i>	83.6	61	28.0	30
872	Bunting, Cinnamon-breasted	<i>Emberiza tahapisi</i>	8.2	6	0.0	0
874	Bunting, Golden-breasted	<i>Emberiza flaviventris</i>	11.0	8	2.8	3
717	Bushshrike, Olive	<i>Chlorophoneus olivaceus</i>	17.8	13	0.9	1
227	Bustard, Black-bellied	<i>Lissotis melanogaster</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
219	Bustard, Denham's	<i>Neotis denhami</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
222	Bustard, White-bellied	<i>Eupodotis senegalensis</i>	4.1	3	7.5	8
196	Buttonquail, Common	<i>Turnix sylvaticus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
154	Buzzard, Common	<i>Buteo buteo</i>	39.7	29	10.3	11
152	Buzzard, Jackal	<i>Buteo rufofuscus</i>	49.3	36	14.0	15
627	Camaroptera, Green-backed	<i>Camaroptera brachyura brachyura</i>	8.2	6	0.0	0
860	Canary, Black-throated	<i>Crithagra atrogularis</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
857	Canary, Cape	<i>Serinus canicollis</i>	53.4	39	10.3	11
858	Canary, Forest	<i>Crithagra scotops</i>	9.6	7	1.9	2
859	Canary, Yellow-fronted	<i>Crithagra mozambica</i>	20.5	15	1.9	2
575	Chat, Ant-eating	<i>Myrmecocichla formicivora</i>	74.0	54	30.8	33
569	Chat, Buff-streaked	<i>Campicoloides bifasciatus</i>	68.5	50	27.1	29
570	Chat, Familiar	<i>Oenanthe familiaris</i>	15.1	11	2.8	3
573	Chat, Mocking Cliff	<i>Thamnolaea cinnamomeiventris</i>	12.3	9	2.8	3
631	Cisticola, Cloud	<i>Cisticola textrix</i>	5.5	4	1.9	2
647	Cisticola, Croaking	<i>Cisticola natalensis</i>	11.0	8	2.8	3
648	Cisticola, Lazy	<i>Cisticola aberrans</i>	23.3	17	4.7	5
646	Cisticola, Levillant's	<i>Cisticola tinniens</i>	39.7	29	8.4	9
635	Cisticola, Pale-crowned	<i>Cisticola cinnamomeus</i>	6.8	5	1.9	2
639	Cisticola, Wailing	<i>Cisticola lais</i>	17.8	13	2.8	3
634	Cisticola, Wing-snapping	<i>Cisticola ayresii</i>	56.2	41	18.7	20
629	Cisticola, Zitting	<i>Cisticola juncidis</i>	32.9	24	4.7	5
212	Coot, Red-knobbed	<i>Fulica cristata</i>	17.8	13	4.7	5
50	Cormorant, Reed	<i>Microcarbo africanus</i>	20.5	15	5.6	6
47	Cormorant, White-breasted	<i>Phalacrocorax lucidus</i>	4.1	3	0.9	1

4131	Coucal, Burchell's	<i>Centropus burchellii</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
203	Crake, Black	<i>Zaporina flavirostra</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
216	Crane, Blue	<i>Grus paradisea</i>	37.0	27	18.7	20
214	Crane, Grey Crowned	<i>Balearica regulorum</i>	16.4	12	11.2	12
215	Crane, Wattled	<i>Grus carunculata</i>	1.4	1	6.5	7
523	Crow, Cape	<i>Corvus capensis</i>	11.0	8	5.6	6
350	Cuckoo, African Emerald	<i>Chrysococcyx cupreus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
344	Cuckoo, Black	<i>Cuculus clamosus</i>	38.4	28	5.6	6
352	Cuckoo, Diederik	<i>Chrysococcyx caprius</i>	32.9	24	2.8	3
348	Cuckoo, Jacobin	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
351	Cuckoo, Klaas's	<i>Chrysococcyx klaas</i>	32.9	24	2.8	3
343	Cuckoo, Red-chested	<i>Cuculus solitarius</i>	46.6	34	9.3	10
854	Cuckoo-finch	<i>Anomalospiza imberbis</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
513	Cuckooshrike, Black	<i>Campephaga flava</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
52	Darter, African	<i>Anhinga rufa</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
317	Dove, Laughing	<i>Spilopelia senegalensis</i>	8.2	6	0.0	0
322	Dove, Lemon	<i>Columba larvata</i>	11.0	8	0.0	0
318	Dove, Namaqua	<i>Oena capensis</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
314	Dove, Red-eyed	<i>Streptopelia semitorquata</i>	63.0	46	26.2	28
316	Dove, Ring-necked	<i>Streptopelia capicola</i>	75.3	55	29.9	32
517	Drongo, Fork-tailed	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	67.1	49	19.6	21
95	Duck, African Black	<i>Anas sparsa</i>	6.8	5	2.8	3
96	Duck, Yellow-billed	<i>Anas undulata</i>	20.5	15	6.5	7
143	Eagle, Crowned	<i>Stephanoaetus coronatus</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
138	Eagle, Long-crested	<i>Lophaetus occipitalis</i>	8.2	6	6.5	7
142	Eagle, Martial	<i>Polemaetus bellicosus</i>	4.1	3	0.9	1
133	Eagle, Verreaux's	<i>Aquila verreauxii</i>	9.6	7	0.9	1
137	Eagle, Wahlberg's	<i>Hieraaetus wahlbergi</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
368	Eagle-Owl, Spotted	<i>Bubo africanus</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
58	Egret, Great	<i>Ardea alba</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
60	Egret, Intermediate [x]	<i>Ardea intermedia</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
59	Egret, Little	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
61	Egret, Western Cattle	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	13.7	10	4.7	5
119	Falcon, Amur	<i>Falco amurensis</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
114	Falcon, Lanner	<i>Falco biarmicus</i>	8.2	6	4.7	5
833	Firefinch, African	<i>Lagonosticta rubricata</i>	19.2	14	0.0	0
707	Fiscal, Southern	<i>Lanius collaris</i>	93.2	68	38.3	41
149	Fish Eagle, African	<i>Haliaeetus vocifer</i>	5.5	4	0.9	1
655	Flycatcher, African Dusky	<i>Muscicapa adusta</i>	12.3	9	0.9	1
682	Flycatcher, African Paradise	<i>Terpsiphone viridis</i>	53.4	39	8.4	9
680	Flycatcher, Blue-mantled Crested	<i>Trochocercus cyanomelas</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
665	Flycatcher, Fiscal	<i>Melaenornis silens</i>	8.2	6	2.8	3
664	Flycatcher, Southern Black	<i>Melaenornis pammelaina</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
654	Flycatcher, Spotted	<i>Muscicapa striata</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
173	Francolin, Coqui	<i>Campocolinus coqui</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0

178	Francolin, Red-winged	<i>Scleroptila levaillantii</i>	9.6	7	1.9	2
89	Goose, Egyptian	<i>Alopochen aegyptiaca</i>	41.1	30	12.1	13
88	Goose, Spur-winged	<i>Plectropterus gambensis</i>	42.5	31	13.1	14
160	Goshawk, African	<i>Accipiter tachiro</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
618	Grassbird, Cape	<i>Sphenoeacus afer</i>	28.8	21	5.6	6
616	Grassbird, Fan-tailed	<i>Schoenicola brevirostris</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
6	Grebe, Little	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	23.3	17	8.4	9
551	Greenbul, Sombre	<i>Andropadus importunus</i>	58.9	43	14.0	15
263	Greenshank, Common	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
192	Guineafowl, Helmeted	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	45.2	33	13.1	14
72	Hamerkop	<i>Scopus umbretta</i>	8.2	6	3.7	4
167	Harrier, African Marsh	<i>Circus ranivorus</i>	1.4	1	1.9	2
171	Harrier-Hawk, African	<i>Polyboroides typus</i>	23.3	17	4.7	5
55	Heron, Black-headed	<i>Ardea melanocephala</i>	28.8	21	21.5	23
54	Heron, Grey	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	8.2	6	5.6	6
443	Honeybird, Brown-backed	<i>Prodotiscus regulus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
440	Honeyguide, Greater	<i>Indicator indicator</i>	12.3	9	0.0	0
442	Honeyguide, Lesser	<i>Indicator minor</i>	5.5	4	0.0	0
418	Hoopoe, African	<i>Upupa africana</i>	38.4	28	12.1	13
422	Hornbill, Trumpeter	<i>Bycanistes bucinator</i>	6.8	5	0.0	0
507	House Martin, Common	<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	5.5	4	0.0	0
81	Ibis, African Sacred	<i>Threskiornis aethiopicus</i>	11.0	8	1.9	2
84	Ibis, Hadada	<i>Bostrychia hagedash</i>	76.7	56	32.7	35
82	Ibis, Southern Bald	<i>Geronticus calvus</i>	49.3	36	34.6	37
849	Indigobird, Dusky	<i>Vidua funerea</i>	5.5	4	1.9	2
123	Kestrel, Rock	<i>Falco rupicolus</i>	6.8	5	2.8	3
402	Kingfisher, Brown-hooded	<i>Halcyon albiventris</i>	6.8	5	0.9	1
395	Kingfisher, Giant	<i>Megaceryle maxima</i>	5.5	4	0.0	0
396	Kingfisher, Half-collared	<i>Alcedo semitorquata</i>	8.2	6	0.0	0
397	Kingfisher, Malachite	<i>Corythornis cristatus</i>	21.9	16	0.9	1
394	Kingfisher, Pied	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	11.0	8	0.9	1
130	Kite, Black-winged	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	8.2	6	2.8	3
129	Kite, Yellow-billed	<i>Milvus aegyptius</i>	2.7	2	1.9	2
247	Lapwing, African Wattled	<i>Vanellus senegallus</i>	34.2	25	8.4	9
245	Lapwing, Blacksmith	<i>Vanellus armatus</i>	8.2	6	2.8	3
243	Lapwing, Black-winged	<i>Vanellus melanopterus</i>	5.5	4	1.9	2
242	Lapwing, Crowned	<i>Vanellus coronatus</i>	4.1	3	2.8	3
472	Lark, Botha's	<i>Spizocorys fringillaris</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
4126	Lark, Eastern Long-billed	<i>Certhilauda semitorquata</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
488	Lark, Red-capped	<i>Calandrella cinerea</i>	12.3	9	1.9	2
458	Lark, Rufous-naped	<i>Mirafra africana</i>	35.6	26	6.5	7
474	Lark, Spike-heeled	<i>Chersomanes albofasciata</i>	5.5	4	2.8	3
703	Longclaw, Cape	<i>Macronyx capensis</i>	67.1	49	27.1	29
823	Mannikin, Bronze	<i>Lonchura cucullata</i>	11.0	8	1.9	2
510	Martin, Banded	<i>Neophedina cincta</i>	54.8	40	15.0	16
509	Martin, Brown-throated	<i>Riparia paludicola</i>	5.5	4	4.7	5

506	Martin, Rock	<i>Ptyonoprogne fuligula</i>	11.0	8	0.9	1
508	Martin, Sand	<i>Riparia riparia</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
390	Mousebird, Speckled	<i>Colius striatus</i>	45.2	33	11.2	12
637	Neddicky	<i>Cisticola fulvicapilla</i>	21.9	16	2.8	3
373	Nightjar, Fiery-necked	<i>Caprimulgus pectoralis</i>	5.5	4	0.9	1
374	Nightjar, Freckled	<i>Caprimulgus tristigma</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
521	Oriole, Black-headed	<i>Oriolus larvatus</i>	63.0	46	14.0	15
1	Ostrich, Common	<i>Struthio camelus</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
359	Owl, Western Barn	<i>Tyto alba</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
312	Pigeon, African Olive	<i>Columba arquatrix</i>	15.1	11	4.7	5
311	Pigeon, Speckled	<i>Columba guinea</i>	46.6	34	10.3	11
692	Pipit, African	<i>Anthus cinnamomeus</i>	53.4	39	9.3	10
695	Pipit, Buffy	<i>Anthus vaalensis</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
10877	Pipit, Nicholson's	<i>Anthus nicholsoni</i>	9.6	7	0.9	1
694	Pipit, Plain-backed	<i>Anthus leucophrys</i>	6.8	5	0.0	0
238	Plover, Three-banded	<i>Charadrius tricollaris</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
1049	Prinia, Drakensberg	<i>Prinia hypoxantha</i>	32.9	24	6.5	7
649	Prinia, Tawny-flanked	<i>Prinia subflava</i>	12.3	9	0.9	1
712	Puffback, Black-backed	<i>Dryoscopus cubla</i>	23.3	17	5.6	6
189	Quail, Common	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	28.8	21	5.6	6
844	Quailfinch	<i>Ortygospiza atricollis</i>	12.3	9	1.9	2
805	Quelea, Red-billed	<i>Quelea quelea</i>	6.8	5	1.9	2
524	Raven, White-necked	<i>Corvus albicollis</i>	1.4	1	4.7	5
808	Red Bishop, Southern	<i>Euplectes orix</i>	46.6	34	10.3	11
589	Robin, White-starred	<i>Pogonocichla stellata</i>	6.8	5	0.0	0
581	Robin-Chat, Cape	<i>Cossypha caffra</i>	56.2	41	12.1	13
578	Robin-Chat, Chorister	<i>Cossypha dichroa</i>	17.8	13	0.9	1
559	Rock-Thrush, Cape	<i>Monticola rupestris</i>	11.0	8	1.9	2
511	Saw-wing, Black	<i>Psalidoprocne pristopectera</i>	41.1	30	3.7	4
588	Scrub Robin, White-browed	<i>Cercotrichas leucophrys</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
105	Secretarybird	<i>Sagittarius serpentarius</i>	47.9	35	10.3	11
867	Seedeater, Streaky-headed	<i>Crithagra gularis</i>	15.1	11	1.9	2
90	Shelduck, South African	<i>Tadorna cana</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
708	Shrike, Red-backed	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
250	Snipe, African	<i>Gallinago nigripennis</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
786	Sparrow, Cape	<i>Passer melanurus</i>	8.2	6	0.0	0
784	Sparrow, House	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	13.7	10	0.0	0
4142	Sparrow, Southern Grey-headed	<i>Passer diffusus</i>	42.5	31	6.5	7
788	Sparrow, Yellow-throated Bush	<i>Gymnoris superciliaris</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
159	Sparrowhawk, Black	<i>Accipiter melanoleucus</i>	4.1	3	0.9	1
156	Sparrowhawk, Rufous-breasted	<i>Accipiter rufiventris</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
85	Spoonbill, African	<i>Platalea alba</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
185	Spurfowl, Swainson's	<i>Pternistis swainsonii</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
746	Starling, Pied	<i>Lamprotornis bicolor</i>	6.8	5	2.8	3

745	Starling, Red-winged	<i>Onychognathus morio</i>	39.7	29	12.1	13
736	Starling, Violet-backed	<i>Cinnyricinclus leucogaster</i>	20.5	15	1.9	2
576	Stonechat, African	<i>Saxicola torquatus</i>	75.3	55	29.9	32
79	Stork, Black	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	1.4	1	1.9	2
80	Stork, White	<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>	16.4	12	11.2	12
772	Sunbird, Amethyst	<i>Chalcomitra amethystina</i>	45.2	33	4.7	5
758	Sunbird, Greater Double-collared	<i>Cinnyris afer</i>	46.6	34	9.3	10
751	Sunbird, Malachite	<i>Nectarinia famosa</i>	16.4	12	2.8	3
760	Sunbird, Southern Double-collared	<i>Cinnyris chalybeus</i>	12.3	9	3.7	4
493	Swallow, Barn	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	52.1	38	14.0	15
502	Swallow, Greater Striped	<i>Cecropis cucullata</i>	68.5	50	11.2	12
503	Swallow, Lesser Striped	<i>Cecropis abyssinica</i>	5.5	4	0.9	1
504	Swallow, South African Cliff	<i>Petrochelidon spilodera</i>	23.3	17	8.4	9
495	Swallow, White-throated	<i>Hirundo albigularis</i>	24.7	18	2.8	3
208	Swamphen, African	<i>Porphyrio madagascariensis</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
380	Swift, African Black	<i>Apus barbatus</i>	21.9	16	2.8	3
387	Swift, African Palm	<i>Cypsiurus parvus</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
386	Swift, Alpine	<i>Tachymarptis melba</i>	6.8	5	0.9	1
384	Swift, Horus	<i>Apus horus</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
385	Swift, Little	<i>Apus affinis</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
383	Swift, White-rumped	<i>Apus caffer</i>	12.3	9	0.0	0
715	Tchagra, Black-crowned	<i>Tchagra senegalus</i>	23.3	17	1.9	2
97	Teal, Red-billed	<i>Anas erythrorhyncha</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
305	Tern, Whiskered	<i>Chlidonias hybrida</i>	4.1	3	3.7	4
275	Thick-knee, Spotted	<i>Burhinus capensis</i>	16.4	12	0.0	0
557	Thrush, Groundscraper	<i>Turdus litsitsirupa</i>	6.8	5	2.8	3
552	Thrush, Kurrichane	<i>Turdus libonyana</i>	8.2	6	0.9	1
1105	Thrush, Olive	<i>Turdus olivaceus</i>	28.8	21	1.9	2
527	Tit, Southern Black	<i>Melaniparus niger</i>	15.1	11	0.9	1
393	Trogon, Narina	<i>Apaloderma narina</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
4133	Turaco, Knysna	<i>Tauraco corythaix</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
106	Vulture, Cape	<i>Gyps coprotheres</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
685	Wagtail, African Pied	<i>Motacilla aguimp</i>	15.1	11	1.9	2
686	Wagtail, Cape	<i>Motacilla capensis</i>	69.9	51	22.4	24
688	Wagtail, Mountain	<i>Motacilla clara</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
610	Warbler, Barratt's	<i>Bradypterus barratti</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
599	Warbler, Willow	<i>Phylloscopus trochilus</i>	4.1	3	0.0	0
671	Warbler, Yellow-throated Woodland	<i>Phylloscopus ruficapilla</i>	12.3	9	0.0	0
839	Waxbill, Blue	<i>Uraeginthus angolensis</i>	1.4	1	1.9	2
843	Waxbill, Common	<i>Estrilda astrild</i>	46.6	34	15.0	16
825	Waxbill, Swee	<i>Coccyzygia melanotis</i>	6.8	5	0.0	0
799	Weaver, Cape	<i>Ploceus capensis</i>	28.8	21	5.6	6
803	Weaver, Southern Masked	<i>Ploceus velatus</i>	46.6	34	6.5	7

791	Weaver, Spectacled	<i>Ploceus ocularis</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
804	Weaver, Thick-billed	<i>Amblyospiza albifrons</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
797	Weaver, Village	<i>Ploceus cucullatus</i>	28.8	21	2.8	3
1172	White-eye, Cape	<i>Zosterops virens</i>	67.1	49	13.1	14
846	Whydah, Pin-tailed	<i>Vidua macroura</i>	50.7	37	14.0	15
816	Widowbird, Fan-tailed	<i>Euplectes axillaris</i>	58.9	43	11.2	12
818	Widowbird, Long-tailed	<i>Euplectes progne</i>	39.7	29	21.5	23
813	Widowbird, Red-collared	<i>Euplectes ardens</i>	46.6	34	6.5	7
814	Widowbird, White-winged	<i>Euplectes albonotatus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
450	Woodpecker, Cardinal	<i>Dendropicos fuscescens</i>	5.5	4	0.0	0
447	Woodpecker, Golden-tailed	<i>Campethera abingoni</i>	5.5	4	0.0	0
445	Woodpecker, Ground	<i>Geocolaptes olivaceus</i>	4.1	3	0.9	1
452	Woodpecker, Olive	<i>Dendropicos griseocephalus</i>	32.9	24	2.8	3
453	Wryneck, Red-throated	<i>Jynx ruficollis</i>	26.0	19	8.4	9
666	Yellow Warbler, African	<i>Iduna natalensis</i>	11.0	8	0.0	0

Table 3. Birds seen only once or twice in the KPE.

Ref	Common name	Scientific name	Fp	Fpn	Ad	Adn
673	Batis, Chinspot	<i>Batis molitor</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
810	Bishop, Yellow	<i>Euplectes capensis</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
546	Brownbul, Terrestrial	<i>Phyllastrephus terrestris</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
11491	Bulbul, Common	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>	2.7	2	1.9	2
227	Bustard, Black-bellied	<i>Lissotis melanogaster</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
219	Bustard, Denham's	<i>Neotis denhami</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
196	Buttonquail, Common	<i>Turnix sylvaticus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
860	Canary, Black-throated	<i>Crithagra atrogularis</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
4131	Coucal, Burchell's	<i>Centropus burchellii</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
203	Crake, Black	<i>Zaporina flavirostra</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
215	Crane, Wattled	<i>Grus carunculata</i>	1.4	1	6.5	7
350	Cuckoo, African Emerald	<i>Chrysococcyx cupreus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
348	Cuckoo, Jacobin	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
854	Cuckoo-finch	<i>Anomalospiza imberbis</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
513	Cuckooshrike, Black	<i>Campephaga flava</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
52	Darter, African	<i>Anhinga rufa</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
143	Eagle, Crowned	<i>Stephanoaetus coronatus</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
137	Eagle, Wahlberg's	<i>Hieraaetus wahlbergi</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
58	Egret, Great	<i>Ardea alba</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
60	Egret, Intermediate [x]	<i>Ardea intermedia</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
59	Egret, Little	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
119	Falcon, Amur	<i>Falco amurensis</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
664	Flycatcher, Southern Black	<i>Melaenornis pammelaina</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
654	Flycatcher, Spotted	<i>Muscicapa striata</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
173	Francolin, Coqui	<i>Campocolinus coqui</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
616	Grassbird, Fan-tailed	<i>Schoenicola brevirostris</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
263	Greenshank, Common	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0

167	Harrier, African Marsh	<i>Circus ranivorus</i>	1.4	1	1.9	2
443	Honeybird, Brown-backed	<i>Prodotiscus regulus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
129	Kite, Yellow-billed	<i>Milvus aegyptius</i>	2.7	2	1.9	2
472	Lark, Botha's	<i>Spizocorys fringillaris</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
4126	Lark, Eastern Long-billed	<i>Certhilauda semitorquata</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
508	Martin, Sand	<i>Riparia riparia</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
1	Ostrich, Common	<i>Struthio camelus</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
359	Owl, Western Barn	<i>Tyto alba</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
695	Pipit, Buffy	<i>Anthus vaalensis</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
524	Raven, White-necked	<i>Corvus albicollis</i>	1.4	1	4.7	5
588	Scrub Robin, White-browed	<i>Cercotrichas leucophrys</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
90	Shelduck, South African	<i>Tadorna cana</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
156	Sparrowhawk, Rufous-breasted	<i>Accipiter rufiventris</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
85	Spoonbill, African	<i>Platalea alba</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
185	Spurfowl, Swainson's	<i>Pternistis swainsonii</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
79	Stork, Black	<i>Ciconia nigra</i>	1.4	1	1.9	2
208	Swamphen, African	<i>Porphyrio madagascariensis</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
387	Swift, African Palm	<i>Cypsiurus parvus</i>	2.7	2	0.9	1
384	Swift, Horus	<i>Apus horus</i>	2.7	2	0.0	0
385	Swift, Little	<i>Apus affinis</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
97	Teal, Red-billed	<i>Anas erythrorhyncha</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
4133	Turaco, Knysna	<i>Tauraco corythaix</i>	0.0	0	0.9	1
106	Vulture, Cape	<i>Gyps coprotheres</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
688	Wagtail, Mountain	<i>Motacilla clara</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
610	Warbler, Barratt's	<i>Bradypterus barratti</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
839	Waxbill, Blue	<i>Uraeginthus angolensis</i>	1.4	1	1.9	2
791	Weaver, Spectacled	<i>Ploceus ocularis</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0
804	Weaver, Thick-billed	<i>Amblyospiza albifrons</i>	1.4	1	0.9	1
814	Widowbird, White-winged	<i>Euplectes albonotatus</i>	1.4	1	0.0	0

Table 4. Birds recorded in Fp cards in the KPE but not in the Wakkerstroom pentad.

Ref	Common name	Scientific name
673	Batis, Chinspot	<i>Batis molitor</i>
410	Bee-eater, Little	<i>Merops pusillus</i>
542	Blackcap, Bush	<i>Lioptilus nigricapillus</i>
546	Brownbul, Terrestrial	<i>Phyllastrephus terrestris</i>
11491	Bulbul, Common	<i>Pycnonotus barbatus</i>
627	Camaroptera, Green-backed	<i>Camaroptera brachyura brachyura</i>
215	Crane, Wattled	<i>Grus carunculata</i>
348	Cuckoo, Jacobin	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>
350	Cuckoo, African Emerald	<i>Chrysococcyx cupreus</i>
513	Cuckooshrike, Black	<i>Campephaga flava</i>
322	Dove, Lemon	<i>Columba larvata</i>
664	Flycatcher, Southern Black	<i>Melaenornis pammelaina</i>

680	Flycatcher, Blue-mantled Crested	<i>Trochocercus cyanomelas</i>
173	Francolin, Coqui	<i>Campocolinus coqui</i>
616	Grassbird, Fan-tailed	<i>Schoenicola brevirostris</i>
422	Hornbill, Trumpeter	<i>Bycanistes bucinator</i>
849	Indigobird, Dusky	<i>Vidua funerea</i>
472	Lark, Botha's	<i>Spizocorys fringillaris</i>
374	Nightjar, Freckled	<i>Caprimulgus tristigma</i>
312	Pigeon, African Olive	<i>Columba arquatrix</i>
589	Robin, White-starred	<i>Pogonocichla stellata</i>
578	Robin-Chat, Chorister	<i>Cossypha dichroa</i>
760	Sunbird, Southern Double-collared	<i>Cinnyris chalybeus</i>
527	Tit, Southern Black	<i>Melaniparus niger</i>
393	Trogon, Narina	<i>Apaloderma narina</i>
106	Vulture, Cape	<i>Gyps coprotheres</i>
688	Wagtail, Mountain	<i>Motacilla clara</i>
671	Warbler, Yellow-throated Woodland	<i>Phylloscopus ruficapilla</i>
839	Waxbill, Blue	<i>Uraeginthus angolensis</i>
791	Weaver, Spectacled	<i>Ploceus ocularis</i>